

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF COMPLEX SENTENCES (ON THE MATERIAL OF THE SCIENTIFIC TEXT)

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Abstract: *The article is based on investigation of complex sentence and their linguistic features and simultaneously it study a scientific text the framework of its functional and stylistic features in relation to a complex sentence as a construct text as a whole. The syntactic features of a complex sentence are studied, as well as modern approaches to comprehending of a complex sentence, taking into account the corresponding syntactic transformations.*

The influence of the syntactic structure of a complex sentence on the choice of a translation strategy when translating a scientific text from English into Uzbek is determined.

Key words: *scientific functional style; scientific text; functional and stylistic characteristics of a scientific text; syntactic structure of a complex sentence; complex sentence syntax; translation strategy.*

The purpose of this investigation is to study the transformational features of the syntactic structure of a complex sentence in the translation of a scientific text from English into Uzbek and systematization of the methods of transferring the syntactic structure of the sentence of the original text. The tasks of this work include consideration of a scientific text within the framework of its functional and stylistic features; to identify the functional and stylistic characteristics of a scientific text in relation to a complex sentence as a text construct generally; consider modern approaches to the translation of a complex sentence, taking into account the appropriate syntactic transformations and determine the influence of the syntactic structure of a complex sentence on the choice of a translation strategy when translating a scientific text from English into Uzbek.

A complex sentence, being an obligatory element of a scientific text, combines various structured segments of the syntax of the English language, which must be learned and correctly used in the process of translating complex sentences from English into Uzbek. A complex sentence includes not only structural elements, such as nominative-predicative parts as constituent segments of a single complex syntactic form, it also contains a complex semantic load that must be conveyed to the translator as fully as possible. Quite an important influence on the lexical-semantic content of a complex sentence is exerted by its syntactic structure. Structural-component units of a sentence with a complex syntax contain one important feature: the structure of a complex sentence contains components, representing their meaning and content, separate syntactic units with their own completely independent function. Thus, the relevance of the problem of converting syntactic structures of complex sentence is the need to develop a strategy for translating complex sentences in English scientific texts. The scientific novelty of the work lies in the fact that it attempts to examine in detail the process of translating a complex sentence in the text space of a scientific style.

In the field of syntactic and pragmatic studies of the language system, the syntactic structure of a complex proposals are the subject of theoretical discussions. In the theory and practice of translation, the sentence is connected with the problem of correlation of the syntactic "nature" of the sentence with its translation. This specificity of the embodiment of the syntactic structure of a sentence in its lexico-semantic sense is fully reflected in the study of the sentence as a multilevel object of translation activity.

The function of a simple syntax element within a complex sentence is certainly not "self-limited." Any function of a simple syntax element in a complex sentence has its own influence on the translation process. In addition, a simple syntax element in a complex sentence is directly transposed into a complex set of syntax elements of a higher order.

The design of a complex sentence as a syntactic integrity plays an important role in choosing a translation strategy, given that the translator will not deal with a

single one, isolated sentence. The object of translation, as a rule, is the text, which is complex interconnection and combination of sentences, both simple and complex. But if the syntax of a simple sentence (provided that it is not complicated by constructions and phrases) basically contains uncomplicated syntactic constructions, the transformation of which is carried out by the translator.

Sentence syntax variants are expressed in specific functional styles, in accordance with the "canons" of which texts of different levels of complexity and understanding are created. The text itself is a certain "linguistic and communicative field" [4, p. 8], on which the transmission of relevant information and, consequently, awareness and understanding of certain issues and problems is based. Of course, the fact of the important role of the scientific text as an object of translation activity cannot be ignored due to the rather detailed elaboration of translation problems related to this topic. At the same time, most researchers in the field of translation of scientific texts concentrated on studying the scientific text as an object of translation as a whole and did not concretize their research on certain aspects of syntax. However, most studies of the problematic of the syntax of a complex sentence in a scientific text are coupled with a certain linguistic and specific translation phenomenon [1, p. 43]. The closest to the syntax of a complex sentence in the English language are the lexical and grammatical aspects of the functional style of the language, including the scientific style. Concretizing the above, it can be argued that the syntax of a complex sentence and syntactic phenomena in the English language are inextricably linked with each other. The structure of the sentence is the direct "embodiment" of its lexical and grammatical content, which together forms a unity of multilevel components of a syntactic unit of a complex order.

Speech in any language is capable of realizing almost any linguistic potential through the act of communication. The linguistic potential of a scientific text is also notable for the fact that it contains a certain paradigm of linguistic and syntactic interrelationships capable of carrying out a stylistic "visualization" of the content of scientific information. It is the process of transferring information in a scientific text that is essentially an individualized act of concretizing the lexical and syntactic

components of the language. The relationship of the language of the scientific functional style in English to a certain objectified scientific text (natural science, technical, humanitarian content) is considered by many researchers of scientific texts in the English language as a facet of the relationship between language and style.

In the order of the arrangement of these structures in a simple sentence, then in a complex sentence the matter is different. The syntax of a complex sentence for a translator contains a very complex component, which consists in the translator's search for "meaningful" and similar syntactic structures in the target language, taking into account their coherence and compatibility in a single "matter" of a complex sentence.

There is a clear tendency in the scientific text to apply uniform principles of organizing language means. When characterizing scientific texts in English, particular importance should be given to creative elements that can be realized in the presentation of scientific information. It is generally accepted that a scientific text should contain objectively rigorous information, without any "foreign style" inclusions. However, we also support the point of view of most researchers of the functional styles of the language that the boundaries between functional styles are very flexible with some exceptions - for example, it is the official business style [5, p. 173].

A scientific text is a set of information acts, objectified in the form of lexical, grammatical and syntactic components. For texts of a scientific functional style, the use of certain lexical units expressing terminology, grammatical structures (parts of speech, word formation) and the syntactic integrity of information components of the communicative space is characteristic. In a scientific text, a stylistic component can be clearly expressed, which is a manifestation of the individual author's style. The basis of a scientific text itself remains invariant. It is transformed by the author based on the subjective understanding of the "readability" of the information. This primarily applies to scientific texts that contain subjects of humanitarian knowledge, for example, many issues of the humanities, such as: linguistics, translation theory, philosophy, political science, sociology - are debatable, which requires the author to

be creative. when creating material sources of scientific information containing knowledge primarily in the humanities. When analyzing the features of the scientific functional style, it is important to take into account the individuality of the author's style, because the elements of its manifestation, as it were, facilitate the perception of the information contained in the text, and make it possible to eliminate the impression of monotony that is created in some cases when reading scientific papers. A scientific text is a specially organized closed chain of sentences linked by a common communicative goal. This is expressed through communicative integrity, i.e. communicatively, the subsequent sentence builds on the previous one, moving the statement from the known to the new. As a result, a theme-rhematic chain is formed, which has a finite character and determines the boundaries of the text [6, p. 53].

To understand the essence of a complex sentence in a scientific text, it should be noted that it represents event or situational nominations that represent relationships between events in reality. In turn, an event or a situation is a combination of participants, persons or objects related to each other by certain relationships, which makes it possible to consider complex sentences as forms of nomination, denoting situations that include two or more events. Being forms of complex nomination, complex sentences are able to represent the relationship between the events of objective reality, somehow temporary, causal, conditional, concessive, goals, consequences, modes of action and comparison. An important role here belongs to unions used to combine simple sentences into a single syntactic "aggregate" (within a compound sentence) or to include subordinate clauses in a compound sentence. In a complex sentence, unions convey information about relationships and connections between events of objective reality, thus performing a nominative function. As a unit of a complex nomination, the proposal correlates with the situation, i.e. possesses predicativeness. In this sense, a sentence is rightfully considered as a predicative unit of language, with the help of which a predicative (correlating content with reality) unit of thinking is reproduced. Communication and

nomination reflect such relationships between the phenomena of reality, which are characterized as predicative relationships.

In order to express directly the features of the translation of a complex sentence in English, as well as modern approaches to the translation of a complex sentence, we considered it necessary to dwell on the information aspects of the translation of a complex sentence and, first of all, the basics of forming such information in a scientific text. When reading and subsequent translation of a scientific text, it is necessary to understand the structure of scientific knowledge as a whole and what forms such knowledge at the linguistic-semantic level.

When translating a complex sentence of a scientific text from English into Russian, it is necessary to take into account informational factors that determine the process of written translation. The difference between the amount of information that makes up the informational richness of a scientific text and the amount of information that makes it informative for the recipient-translator depends on the limits of distinguishability, in other words, on the interpreter's properties, which are based on the structure of the translation thesaurus [7, p. 224].

The peculiarity of the informative component in the process of translating a complex sentence from English into Russian and in the entire translation process as a whole lies in the way of processing the original information, which leads to a significant or insignificant modification of information at various levels of the language. This is implemented directly in a sentence, including a complex sentence in the English language. As a result of these modifications, additional, mainly pragmatic information penetrates into the translated text and the sentence in particular, which is directly influenced by:

- a) the personal qualities of the translator;
- b) the structure of his thesaurus in comparison with the original;
- c) the nature of the interaction between the original thesaurus and the translator's thesaurus.

The material indicator of this additional information is the discrepancy in the information status between the units of the original and translated texts, which is

especially important when translating a complex sentence in an English scientific text [3, p. 114]. At the same time, any translation modifications have the specifics of transformational process and position themselves in the theory and practice of translation as translation techniques.

The main problem in the process of transmitting the syntactic structure of a complex sentence is the processing by the translator of grammatical constructions that have no analogues in the target language. In the process of translation, the main task is to extract the meaning in a complex sentence and its adequate transmission [2, p. 327].

Public opinion is lukewarm; although Europeans generally support a bigger role for the EU in international security, they are very skeptical of operations of a peace-enforcement nature [8, p. 43]. / Jamoatchilik fikri iliq; Evropaliklar, odatda, xalqaro xavfsizlik masalasida Evropa Ittifoqining katta rolini qo'llab-quvvatlasalar-da, ular tinchlikparvarlik amaliyotiga juda shubha bilan qaraydilar

This sentence is complex, contains elements of both subordination and compositional communication. A compositional connection in a complex sentence is expressed in punctuation between the first simple sentence (*Jamoatchilik fikri iliq*) and the rest of the sentence with a complex subordinate connection. Within the entire complex sentence there is a subordinate clause of the assignment (*Evropaliklar, odatda, xalqaro xavfsizlik masalasida Evropa Ittifoqining katta rolini qo'llab-quvvatlasalar-da, ular tinchlikparvarlik amaliyotiga juda shubha bilan qaraydilar*) When translating this sentence, we made the following syntactic replacements: division of sentences - this transformation was necessary due to the different punctuation of complex sentences in English and Uzbek; At the level of a phrase, we made syntactic replacements in a phrase (*inchlikparvarlik amaliyotiga*), in which the attributive part of a phrase in English was transformed into a phrase with a prepositional construction (*operations of a peace-enforcement nature*).

When analyzing the translation of complex sentences in a scientific text, we used the following syntactic transformations: division and combination of sentences, replacement of sentence members, replacement of the type of sentences. We applied

such transformations taking into account the semantic coherence of the informative field of the English complex sentence. The lexico-semantic content of a scientific text required the use of complex syntactic units overloaded with information, which created certain difficulties in translation. One of the basic problems of translating a complex sentence in a scientific text lies in the selection of the necessary syntactic structure that would most fully correspond to the semantic content of an equivalent syntactic unit.

Thus, as a unit of translation, a complex sentence is subject to translation transformations, among which there are various approaches to ways of transforming its syntactic structure in English. It is necessary to take into account the degree of information content of a complex sentence in any approach to its translation from English into Russian. First of all, this manifests itself in endowing a complex sentence with such a universal, extralinguistic quality as informative value, since with such an interpretation of the function of a complex sentence in a linguistic communicative space, i.e. the ability to include in its syntactic structure certain meanings embedded in the lexical "palette" of the information chain of a complex sentence, the method of translation transformations at the syntax level may differ.

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